

Some Social Aspects of the Soul of Multiverse Hypothesis

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Abstract

As a continuation of this author's previous cosmological neuroscience papers on the hypothesized Soul of Multiverse and its possible laws, the present work examined the social aspects of four of these laws. The following key aspects were recognized: (1) Knowing about the cosmic Law of Coexistence in Diversity can let our mind respect not only the endless diversity of human beings but also the cohesive force of space-time in which all are connected. This may help realizing the superiority of cooperation for shared goals over competition for gaining by harming others. (2) Knowing about the cosmic Law of Truth in Complexity can ready our mind to confront the problems of societies with the understanding that these problems are much more complex than generally thought. This may help initiating the needed intellectual renaissance of the 21st century. (3) Knowing about the cosmic Law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry can make our mind appreciate the slight yet sufficient supremacy of divine over evil. This may help restoring faith in the eventual creation of a just society, where social justice is defined as an administrative mechanism providing the right conditions for every human being to accomplish his or her Conscience-led Mission throughout life, while allowing each of these accomplishments to be reciprocated with the gratitude it induced in the involved social systems, small or large, to let equal opportunities in life coexist with due diversity in welcomed, not abused, social recognitions. And (4) knowing about the cosmic Law of Lives to Transcend can empower our mind to build on these advances. This may help moving evolution towards the human species worthy of its origin and destination.

Key Words: soul, prefrontal cortex, multiverse, noosphere, conscience, social justice, Government of Earth

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Introduction

An integrative look into the philosophical layers of my previous neuroscientific (Ludvig, 1999, 2000; Fenton *et al.*, 2008), neuroengineering (Ludvig *et al.*, 2011, 2016) and literary (Ludvig, 1988, 2017) works led me to propose that the central medium of

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human Soul is a prefrontal cortical neural supercircuitry functioning as Self-Ken for representing the host's Identity, Conscience, Will and Mission (Ludvig, 2022a, b). I went further to suggest that analogous phenomena exist at global and cosmic scales with both phenomena related to a Soul of Multiverse (Ludvig, 2022a, b) imagined in ancient sacred texts as Purusha, Tao, Holy Spirit and other similar concepts.

Do these thoughts have some practicality? Can they be used for something?

In my opinion, considering the examined cosmic laws may shed new light on some social problems and may help us to move closer to the solution of these problems. Because the destruction of Ukrainian towns in 2022 for the command of a Russian leader heading a government of looters (Lane, 2022); the refugee camp system all over the world, like the one in Sudan, as a consequence of war zones in Africa and Asia due to international politics unmanageable by an obsolete United Nations; or the January 6, 2021, attack on the US Capitol by a mob supporting a President upset by not being reelected (**Figure 1**), are indications of severe social problems from Asia and Europe to Africa and America.

The present article aims to contribute to the understanding of the origin and nature of these social problems by looking into the social aspects of the following possible laws of the Soul of Multiverse: Coexistence in Diversity, Truth in Complexity, Divine - Evil Asymmetry and Lives to Transcend.

Figure 1. Left panel: Photograph made in the Ukrainian town of Mariupol after an attack by the Russian military, as reported by Reuters and Jerusalem Post on April 12, 2022. Central panel: Ethiopian refugees in the Um Rakuba camp, Sudan, on February 19, 2021, as photographed by Hussein Ery for AFP/Getty Images. Right panel: Scene at the Us Capitol on January 6, 2021, as photographed by Lev Radin for Pacific Press/Light Rocket/Getty Images.

Though the doubting reader will surely ask: Do we need to understand social problems? Shouldn't they be treated as unchangeable consequences of human nature? Indeed, hasn't every social arrangement since the dawn of civilization ended up in failure to be replaced with a new system, which headed to its own failure decades or centuries later? If so, why spending time on trying to solve the unsolvable? Is not seeking personal happiness enough a job for a lifetime, whether in just or unjust societies? In fact, what is social justice? By the end of this article, these questions will also be answered.

Society and the cosmic law of Coexistence in Diversity

Coexistence in Diversity can be defined as a cosmic law guarded by the Soul of Multiverse to let the common substance of matter and energy in the fabric of space-time evolve with variations as inexhaustible as dependable on their connecting interactions.

For example, if someone analyzed what takes place in and around the Puerto Rican *Arecibo*, the Chinese *FAST*, the Spanish *GTC*, the Hawaiian *Keck I* and *Keck II* and the South African *SALT* telescopes in the same minute, he or she could see that each has a different design, collects different sets of data, surrounded by a different flora, and run by people with not less different mindsets, dreams and family lives. An inexhaustible diversity can be seen in either of these locations, however each is billion times smaller than the surface of Earth.

And this just indicates that Diversity is an essential attribute of the common substance of matter and energy in space.

For Diversity is also an essential attribute of the common substance of matter and energy in time, which is nothing else than one of the manifestations of this common substance's eternal move. Indeed, every millisecond in its flow has a new set of events (e.g., new action potential streams in brains (Ludvig, 1999; 2000)) – though changes in time are more evident when larger time-waves are compared. For example, no human intelligence was present at any of these telescope locations just a million years ago. But 10,000 years ago, human intelligence already thrived at all five places – though the inhabitants of neither place had any idea about the existence of the other four. Then people in the last century could witness at each the construction and use of telescopes. Of which advanced versions once will orbit around the Moon and the Mars.

Yet, all of these specific diversities are connected and governed by the cohesive force of Coexistence, as manifested at the telescope-sites in astronomical collaboration, data exchange, personal visits, international support and many other related acts to serve the common goal of learning about the Universe.

Coexistence in Diversity: as simple as the difficulty of grasping the overarching command and social meaning of the Law behind it. The *Bhagavad Gita*, created more than 2,000 years ago in unknown circumstances, is among the most majestic products of the human mind. Yet, in Chapter 2, when Arjuna is conflicted before the battle against his competing family members: “*Shall I kill my own masters who, though greedy of my kingdom, are yet my sacred teachers?*”, his God, Krishna, has this answer to him “*Think you also of your duty and do not waver. There is no greater good for a warrior than to fight in a righteous war.*” That the world is large enough to let diverse interests coexist without going to war, this was beyond even the sacred text's author.

One of the incomparable geniuses of humankind, Muhammad, taught in his *Farewell Sermon* that “... an Arab has no superiority over a non-Arab nor a non-Arab has any superiority over an Arab; also, a white has no superiority over a black nor a black has any superiority over white except by piety and good action...” Yet, his followers killed each other on the battlefield of Karbala because of their different opinions on “good action” and forced non-Arabs into servitude in three continents.

History rarely let as superior intellects working on the blueprint of a new society as Thomas Jefferson, Benjamin Franklin and John Adams were in the supporting company of Roger Sherman and Robert R. Livingston. Their Declaration of Independence in 1776 stunned the world with the statement that “*We hold these truths to be self-evident, that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable Rights, that among these are Life, Liberty and the pursuit of Happiness.*” But their Bible-based concept of “all men” did not extend to Native Americans nor to men of African origin. And it did not occur to even Jefferson that the “*unalienable Rights*” of men should coexist with the same “*unalienable Rights*” of women.

How were these possible? These were possible because the Law of Truth in Complexity permeating complicated social dynamics was hardly understood in the time of the births of religions, nor even at the beginning of the modern era, when wars were viewed as acts inseparable from human life and slaveholding as a right of the highest classes. Also, the Law of Divine – Evil Asymmetry let such evil practices as exploitation of the weak by the strong be the norm of social relationships. Yet, the interactions of all of these laws with the Law of Lives to Transcend make the most complicated social dynamics understood sooner or later and render the most horrible social practices temporary only. I support these thoughts with the visual message of **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Photograph taken on a BBC News clip titled “Meghan Markle gives fan a hug while meeting with mourners at Windsor Castle” (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aAIKK8cmpXU>). The Law of Coexistence in Diversity allowed this embrace happen between a former American actress born with genes of African origin and an English teen belonging to the very people who once colonized Africa and view royalty as the privilege of their own nation’s best. And the Law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry let this simple hug with magnanimity and freedom counteract all media attacks and business manipulations against Meghan and her husband. The image also conveys the Law of Lives to Transcend, that disadvantaged births, like Meghan’s, can evolve into carriers of worldwide impact while average births, like the teen’s, can evolve into carriers of freedom to love the magnanimous.

Thus, knowing about the hypothesized cosmic law of Coexistence in Diversity can help our mind to respect not only the endless diversity of human personalities and physical appearances but also the cohesive force of space-time in which these personalities and physical appearances come to existence. As a consequence, we may feel natural to improve on our social environment with the tools of reasonable cooperation instead of unreasonable competition, including the cooperative traits of magnanimity and freedom to love the magnanimous.

Society and the cosmic law of Truth in Complexity

Truth in Complexity can be defined as a cosmic law guarded by the Soul of Multiverse to guide intelligent life to sense, understand and express the inexhaustible and interdependent forms of existence as they are: in the beauty of their complexity, be it difficult, often impossible, to sense, understand and express that complexity as truth.

Because of this difficulty, few could sense the complexity of social interests as Jesus did, who understood that giving to political leaders what belongs to them while “giving to God what belongs to God” can work; that evil must be the most deeply known, not to fight with it just to keep it away; that all people, Jews or not Jews, deserve illumination by the Holy Spirit; or that one’s Mission, good or bad, must be accepted and accomplished – as cups filled with suffering must be taken just as those filled with happiness.

Few could appreciate the complexities of matter, energy, space and time as Tesla and Einstein did, yet precisely because of that complexity even they disagreed with each other. Marc Seifer eloquently captured this disagreement in his recent book: “...Tesla understood ether theory a lot better than Einstein did, but obviously, Tesla also did not truly understand the ultimate nature of atomic structure, that is, in particular the structure of the nucleus... Had he lived a few more years to see the explosion of the atom bomb, Tesla would have been forced to reevaluate what he discarded, and had Einstein reevaluated the full ramifications of Tesla’s ether theory, he may have been able to achieve his grand dream of unifying gravity with electromagnetism, a process explainable by a full understanding of ether theory coupled with Tesla’s dynamic theory of gravity.” (Seifer, 2022).

And few could express the complexity of parent – child relationships as Kahlil Gibran did, grasping the presence of higher-order laws, indeed an overarching Soul, in defining the purpose of a new child’s life, however he used the language of poets when compared this Soul to an “archer”.

Let me elevate this article with the relevant passage from “The Prophet”, his masterpiece: *“Your children are not your children. / They are the sons and daughters of Life’s longing for itself. / They come through you but not from you.../ You are the bows from which your children as living arrows are sent forth. / The archer sees the mark upon the path of the infinite, and He bends you with His might that His arrows may go swift and far.”* (Gibran, 1923).

Don’t these examples prove the cosmic law of Truth in Complexity?

Sure, small things, even the smallest, have their own truth – but each is embedded in the context of its hosting complexity. The truth of the magic of Louis Armstrong’s 2.5-minute song, *“What a Wonderful World”*, is that it conveys thousand times more about the Soul of Multiverse with its simple melody and lyrics than all of the texts and figures of my cosmological neuroscience papers. Yet, this song’s truth is also part of a complexity in space-time where the musician’s slave ancestors are as much present, smiling and forgiving, as the ABC Records chief whose envy worked hard against the success of the song -- of which covers from the heights of Eva Cassidy, Katie Melua, Rod Stewart or Stevie Wonder multiply the nodes of that complexity.

The case of Christopher Columbus particularly shows the necessity of seeing truths as embedded in complexity. If there is indeed a Self-Ken in the human brain, a prefrontal cortical supercircuitry with domains Mission, Will, Identity and Conscience (Ludvig, 2022a, b), then Columbus’ not unlikely mutated neurogenetic network, childhood exposures to the Genovese shore of the Mediterranean Sea, and the unique space-time circumstance of the blockade of lucrative trade routes between Europe to Asia by the rising Ottoman Empire all presented his Self-Ken with a Mission for him and him only: to go on the sea and find a new trade route to Asia – if not eastward then westward.

But he also accepted without hesitation Toscanelli’s erroneous calculation about the distance between Spain and the coast of China, while his almost pathological aspiration to the never-heard rank of “Admiral of the Ocean Sea” strengthened his Will to superhuman levels.

Yet, when he triumphed after a decade of struggles that recreated his Identity, his Conscience didn’t prevent him from being ungrateful to the co-discoverer Pinzón brothers, nor from suggesting in his letter of 1493 to King Ferdinand and Queen Isabella, that *“by some little assistance from them”* he will *“give them as many heathen slaves as their majesties may choose to demand.”*

He didn’t know where his ships landed -- still it was he who opened up the age of exploration.

Despite its complexity, this life has been seen more through the windows of either admiration or hate, and almost never side by side with a native American as forgiving as being a dreamer about collaboration: coexistence in diversity (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Left panel: A shot from the Ridley Scott – Vangelis – Gerard Depardieu film, “1492 Conquest of Paradise”, on Columbus’ historic voyage. The picture shows one of the film’s unforgettable moments that imagined Columbus’ historic landing. Central panel: Columbus’ statues were vandalized in several cities in the United States in 2020. This picture was taken from the CGTN News website, but the events were reported in many newspapers including the *New York Times* (Diaz, 2020). Right panel: A shot from the YouTube clip of Tai Simpson, a descendant of Chief Redheart in the Nez Perce Tribe of Idaho, arguing that there is no history without her people. And she herself said: “...it is possible to live collaboratively to co-create a world...” Less eloquently, this paper intends to convey the same truth.

Thus, knowing about the hypothesized cosmic law of Truth in Complexity can help our mind to confront social problems with the understanding that these problems are necessarily too complex for traditional scientific and governing methods. As a consequence, social problems might be treated better with as much attention to the contexts of global space and time as to details of national character and history. In fact, political problems in the 21st century seem to be impossible to solve without an intercontinental educational renaissance and a new approach to culture that seeks creative inspiration in the past, real impact on the presence and exciting vision for the future, indeed the social application of truth in complexity.

Society and the Cosmic Law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry

Divine - Evil Asymmetry can be defined as a cosmic law guarded, though not generated, by the Soul of Multiverse to admit the necessity of Evil, that is, destruction, discord, degeneration and death in the allness of existence while assuring the subordination of this necessity to the Divine, which is creation, harmony, evolution and life.

This addresses Leibniz’s question of “why there is something rather than nothing” (*24 Metaphysical Theses*; <http://www.leibniz-translations.com/theses.htm>) by indicating that the supremacy of Divine over Evil, due to the Asymmetry of their opposing powers, favors creation over destruction, “something” over “nothing” (however the source of this Asymmetry is beyond even the Soul of Multiverse).

Indeed, the Last Universal Common Ancestors (Glansdorff *et al.*, 2008) moved on the way of *evolution* toward human intelligence instead of the way of *degeneration* into protein/DNA solutes in the first sea; *life* regained its supremacy over *death* after all mass extinctions and World Wars.

Then what are the social aspects of this Law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry?

First, humanity must accept that evil coexists with the divine and is part of the complex truth in every society. Again and again, we must face “demon-haunted worlds” where the reason and goodwill of true science are “candles in the dark” (Sagan, 1996). Students of the Soul of Multiverse join with their own candles – though with ones lit by the reason and goodwill of both true science and true faith laid down in the harmoniously differing texts of the *Principia Mathematica*, *The Origin of Species*, *The Future of Mankind* (Teilhard de Chardin, 1959), *The Astonishing Hypothesis* (Crick, 1994), *On the Future: Prospects for Humanity* (Rees, 2018), the *Zend-Avesta*, *Tao Te Ching*, *Bhagavad Gita*, *Sermon at Benares*, *Torah*, *Gospels*, *Quran*, and other intellectual waves of the same quality.

Second, the asymmetry of divine and evil powers with its slight imbalance favoring the divine must give hope to the weak and the less fortunate -whether at individual, community, or national levels- that neither of them is left alone, that there is a cosmic law for their care.

Third, examination of the Law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry from the vantage point of cosmological neuroscience offers new opportunities to map, understand and control at least some of the evils of social systems, especially the seemingly ever-present and always renewing forms of social injustice. Neuroscience suggests that these injustices are almost always related to abnormal individual Conscience operating in the minds of wrongly selected leaders and the mass-men these leaders recruit for their cause. Robespierre found his executioners to support his terror, Hitler found his officers, philosophers and engineers to support his. Alexandra Tolstoy, once close to the leaders who organized the invasion and destruction of Ukraine in 2022, told in a CNN interview on March 17 of the same year that the predominant intellectual trait of these leaders was the “complete lack of normal human morals”, that is, a Self-Ken without functioning Conscience.

What neither Robespierre, nor Hitler, nor the invaders of Ukraine knew that their work was possible because the Law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry permits destruction, discord, degeneration and death, just to be overcome, always and everywhere, by the superior forces of creation, harmony, evolution and life (**Fig. 4**).

Figure 4. Left panel: A view of Nagasaki after the drop of the atomic bomb on the city on August 9, 1945, instantly razing most of its buildings and killing about 40,000 civilians. This previously unimaginable destructive effect was already known from the atomic bombing of Hiroshima three days before. It is now known that the Nazi Albert Speer, arrested by American forces on May 15, 1945, recommended to his interrogators the use of the atomic bomb against Japan (Greaves, 2021). Right panel: A present-day photograph of the Hypocenter Memorial in Nagasaki at the site of the drop of the bomb. Obeying to the Law of Coexistence in Diversity, Divine and Evil do coexist. Yet, the Law of Divine – Evil Asymmetry assures the supremacy of the former, so obvious in these juxtaposed images. (At the same time, it is painful to see that the evil of this bomb was needed to end the work of an even more destructive evil, the Pacific War – though higher minds than Speer’s, Oppenheimer’s and Truman’s would probably have let the tragedy of Hiroshima sink in the collective Japanese soul and made peace without erasing another city from the face of the Earth. Though whether circumstances would have allowed it, we will never know.)

Thus, knowing about the hypothesized cosmic law of Divine – Evil Asymmetry can help our mind to understand not just the origin of the unwanted yet necessary presence of evil across the entirety of existence, but also the slight yet sufficient supremacy of the power of divine over the power of evil. And this justifies trust in the eventual creation of a fair society, the one that necessarily led by intellects with moral compass.

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Society and the cosmic law of Lives to Transcend

Lives to Transcend can be defined as a cosmic law guarded by the Soul of Multiverse to assure that life is transmitted to nodes of space-time, like Earth, where life is destined to appear in its imperfect grandeur: always aspiring to higher levels, ever closer to the source of its existence which is also its aim.

This definition agrees with the proposal that lives may be spread in the Universe by *Directed Panspermia* (Crick and Orgel, 1973) and that precisely because of this cosmic spread, errors can slip in its divine programs. Because of these errors, life on Earth is as much a majestic story of simple life-forms transcending into human intelligence as a scene of “imperfect grandeur.”

Cosmological neuroscience considers the following 4 facts as supportive for this definition:

(1) The first cells on Earth, those Last Universal Common Ancestors (Glansdorff *et al.*, 2008), neither degenerated nor stayed the same – instead, their DNA-based molecular program initiated a ~4-billion-year evolution leading to increasingly complex, multicellular organisms that culminated in the appearance of Primates about 60 million years ago. Thus, single cells transcended to high-order animals governed by consciousness.

(2) From the order Primates, a unique animal emerged about 6 million years ago initiating the *hominin* lineage with the interdependent development of anatomical and physiological, including neuroanatomical and neurophysiological, conditions for such diverse abilities as bipedalism, toolmaking, language, socialization, and artistic/spiritual cognition of which complexity produced the species *Homo sapiens* about 300,000 years ago (Stringer 2016). Thus, a Primate lineage transcended to leave the animal world and create civilization.

(3) Once civilized, *Homo sapiens* crossed the threshold of the digital space-age within a cosmic moment of just 10,000 years to earn the prospect of becoming a physically improved, morally reborn and intellectually advanced spacefaring race living in social justice and ready to undertake its cosmic Mission. Whether this evolutionary leap will be led by genetically edited or bionic humans, cooperating or competing with android robots (Kral and Ludvig, 2013; Ludvig, 2021), these are details. The essence is that a planetary civilization is about to transcend to assist the Soul of Multiverse.

(4) These three events are not independent of each other. Rather, they are waves connected by the same direction, the same perseverance, the same expansion, -- and, yes, more likely for the same purpose, however unclear it is to the cosmic child who the 21st century humankind still is.

The Law of Divine – Evil Asymmetry, examined in the previous section, means that the alternatives of humankind's degeneration and/or self-destruction will surely challenge the coming generations. But because of the likely supremacy of divine forces over the evil ones, these alternatives will be discarded, though not before evil is paid with losses and tragedies.

To minimize these losses and tragedies has always been the lifelong aim of the best.

In the Book IV (“Le Jin”) of *Analects*, the posthumous compilation of Confucius' teachings, we are asked to recognize that “*The superior man thinks of virtue; the small man thinks of comfort...The mind of the superior man is conversant with righteousness; the mind of the mean man is conversant with gain.*”

Carl Gustav Jung was clear about the most important political move of humankind: *“Despite all the differences, the unity of mankind will assert itself irresistibly.”* (Jung, 1958).

Thomas Piketty shares with us this truth about social justice in the 21st century: *“We must also describe precisely the transnational assemblies that would ideally be entrusted with global public good and common policies of fiscal and environmental justice.”* (Piketty, 2022). But Piketty also emphasized that *“It would be absurd to claim that such a path is easy to follow and clearly marked out: nearly everything remains to be invented.”* (Piketty, 2022).

What should be invented? The point of this article is that nothing should be invented, as it is enough to process – though meticulously, honestly and creatively – what the cosmic law of Lives to Transcend has been streaming to us since the dawn of civilization.

This streaming has been received through the essence – not the manipulated surface – of religions; through the inspired – not the commercial – forms of art; through the benevolent – not the harmful – products of science; through the humble – not the arrogant – suggestions of philosophy; and through the constructive – not the destructive – achievements of engineering. And reading this stream can tell anyone that our time’s dominant social force of globalization is guided by the cosmic Soul -- as captured in John Lennon’s imagined global home where *“...all the people sharing all the world...”*, where *“...the world will live as one...”*. But this can happen only if Confucius’ *“superior men”* finally undertake the task of *“asserting”* Jung’s *“unity of mankind”* via Piketty’s *“transnational assemblies”* ultimately founding the Government of Earth administered by the trained and chosen morally right and intellectually able for the decent and free.

Many justifiably feel – though can’t prove – that the diametrically opposite version of this Government of Earth is already in the works by a shadowy few who control via personal wealth, historic connections and/or political power the move of social energy, that is, money, across the globe for objectives as shadowy as they themselves are. But the very Law of Divine – Evil Asymmetry suggests that in this competition they will not prevail, as the right global society is saved for the divine.

For this prevailing global administration some social aspects of the Soul of Multiverse hypothesis could be useful to consider.

First, considering the cosmic law of Coexistence in Diversity could help balancing, justly and effectively, the diverse interests of all nations and independent communities, weak or strong – while nurturing the historic and cultural uniqueness, as well as the freedom of national discourse, in each.

Thus, the *Government of Earth*, would be administered by periodically renewing councils of the – trained and chosen – morally right and intellectually able, for the voluntarily joining decent and free who understand that just as our Solar System is moved by the Sun, the emerging global society on Earth also needs a governing body. To serve, not to dictate. To be just. Which is the practice of duty to help each and every human Mission under Conscience to be accomplished.

Second, appreciating the cosmic law of Truth in Complexity could help building the needed *Intercontinental Education System* run by a new noble class, the class of extraordinary teachers and child care professionals devoted to teach every child on the planet about the beauty and usefulness of lifelong learning, tolerance, duty, honor, cooperation and artful communication.

Third, keeping in mind the overarching Divine – Evil Asymmetry could help transforming the military forces of the world to a trusted *System Against Natural and Human-Made Disasters*, on which every single village, city or country on Earth can count on when earthquakes, floods, wildfires, drought and famines, volcano eruptions, hurricanes, Bhopal-, Chernobyl- and Deepwater Horizon-like disasters, or in the distant future asteroids, threaten or strike. Which resulted in the United States alone more than 15,000 deaths and more 2 trillion dollars of economic loss since 1980 (Ritchie & Roser, 2014; NOAA/NCEI Information, 2022).

Fourth, knowing about the cosmic law of Lives to Transcend could help the Government of Earth to restore the global harmony between plants, animals and humans, use the available resources for Earth according to reason and conscience, and advance the ethics of religions of goodness into a common understanding of the Mission of human existence. Which is most likely the next evolutionary step changing us to a species worthy of its origin and destiny. In a way, this is reflected in the – unpublished -- architectural vision of *Humankind's Gate*, a twin-skyscraper looking like wings of a colossal open gate somewhere in a remote East African region for guarding and exhibiting faithful copies of the most representative artistic, scientific, religious, philosophical and engineering products of the human experiment on Earth. The building could become a pilgrimage site at the very region where some members the *Australopithecus afarensis* line started that experiment.

Then what is the answer to the doubting reader's questions acknowledged in the Introduction? The answer is that if the Soul of Multiverse inspired the transmission of life to Earth, as it did, then life must not be just a privilege to enjoy but also a challenge to take: the challenge of using it to transcend to a cosmic presence contributing to the meaning of the allness of existence, and since this cannot happen unless backed by a just global society then this social state must also be built. But to evaluate this answer, the term "just society" needs to be defined. The last section intends to do that.

Social justice in the context of the Soul of Multiverse

The cosmic law, guarded by the Soul of Multiverse, which commands Coexistence in Diversity is one of the reasons of the difficulty of even designing a just society.

Geniuses failed to reconcile the seemingly contradictory facts of diversity among human beings in terms of health, beauty, strength, intellect, creativity, courage, birthright, uprising and wealth with the absolute necessity of their coexistence due to the unchangeable space-time wave they share, whether like it or not. Robespierre, mentioned above, unable to process the need of aristocrats living together with the less fortunate at birth, chose to lead his Reign of Terror by organizing the execution of thousands of aristocrats; Lenin, Trotsky, Stalin and their comrades, unable to process the need of communists and non-communists living together, initiated the killing of millions of people disagreeing with Bolshevik ideas. More peaceful political thinkers were satisfied with just subordinating those who were different from them. The legendary writer – sociologist team in the 1970s Hungary, György Konrád and Iván Szelényi, encouraged like-minded people to form a new ruling class. *“The Intellectuals on the Road to Class Power”*, this was their famous book’s telling title (Konrád & Szelényi, 1979). Social justice? Coexistence in Diversity? Governing a society with not merely shrewd intellectuals but morally living, high-minded visionaries? These were not for them, nor for the plutocrats (Freeland, 2012) who have made their vision our reality (**Figure 1**).

The Law of Truth in Complexity may illuminate the solution. For however diverse the elements and structures of the world are, living or nonliving, Nature moves them together, keeping their unique identities intact while letting their splendid complexity work as it should: balanced and harmonized so long their missions last. We don’t know about the details of the “irreducible complexity” (Behe, 1996) of the original cells on Earth, but those who ever looked into the ultrastructure of neurons, like this author did (Ludvig *et al.*, 1990), seeing a higher truth in the encountered complexity was the most remarkable experience. Similarly, we don’t know whether vibrating strings, permeating ether, dark energy, dark matter or interactions with nearby Universes keep the complexity of our own Universe together – but its complexity is the most revealing truth about its essence. And if so, the nature of social justice can also be understood only if examined in the fabric of human networks’ complexity – because the strong lives alongside the weak, the genius next to the idiot, the aristocrat crosses the same space-time as the abandoned orphan.

Still, the powerful cosmic law of Divine - Evil Asymmetry, responsible for sustaining evil, adds an extra difficulty to the engineering of social justice.

When one of humankind's greatest dreamers, Che Guevara, joined the Cuban effort to replace the country's criminal dictatorship with a better social system, – evil immediately appeared and used him to oversee executions of more than a hundred dissenters as the commander of La Cabaña, distorting the original ideals behind the Cuban movement. When the visionary leader Gorbachev started to purify his country's Soviet-type communism, – evil immediately appeared to contaminate his work with the rise of corruption, wicked capitalism, money-worshipping. When the ingenuity of American scientists and engineers opened up the computer age, – evil immediately appeared and let the guardians of computer systems use their machines for spying, disinformation, economic manipulations (Snowden, 2019; Foroohar, 2019; Haugen, 2021).

But it seems the Soul of Multiverse's Law of Lives to Transcend attracts all these laws and orchestrates their interactions to serve the human phenomenon. Which allows the transcendence of human souls to a state where diversity is embraced by coexistence, complexity radiates the underlying truth, and evil is overpowered by the divine. In this state, social justice is defined as an administrative mechanism providing the right conditions for every human being to accomplish his or her Conscience-led Mission throughout life, while allowing each of these accomplishments to be reciprocated with the gratitude it induced in the involved social systems, small or large, to let equal opportunities in life coexist with due diversity in social recognitions resonating with *noblesse oblige* from the past and *divine duty* from the future.

Conclusions

As a continuation of this author's previous papers on the hypothesized Soul of Multiverse and its possible laws, the present paper examined the social aspects of this sacred phenomenon.

Using the methods of cosmological neuroscience, social aspects of the following possible laws of the Soul of Multiverse were examined: (1) Coexistence in Diversity, (2) Truth in Complexity, (3) Divine - Evil Asymmetry, and (4) Lives to Transcend.

First, it seemed that knowing about the cosmic law of Coexistence in Diversity can let our mind respect not only the endless diversity of human personalities and physical appearances but also the cohesive force of space-time in which both are embedded. In turn, this could inspire work on improving social environments with the tools of tolerance, admiration – for the worthy, and cooperation.

Second, it also seemed that knowing about the cosmic law of Truth in Complexity can ready our mind to confront the problems of societies with the understanding that these problems are much more complex than generally thought. In turn, this could lead to the recognition that social problems are better to be improved with attention to the details of national character and history placed in the fabric of global space and time.

Third, it appeared that knowing about the cosmic law of Divine – Evil Asymmetry can help our mind to understand not just the origin of the unwanted yet necessary presence of evil across the entirety of existence but also the slight yet sufficient supremacy of the power of divine over the power of evil. In turn, this could justify faith in the eventual creation of a just society.

Finally, it was argued that knowing about the cosmic law of Lives to Transcend can inspire our mind to see politics in a context larger than its noisy scene.

In this context, an *Intercontinental Education System* run by the new noble class of extraordinary teachers and child care professionals or the transformation of national armed forces into a worldwide *System Against Natural and Human-Made Disasters* would look as simple and self-explanatory as the design of a skyscraper, *Humankind's Gate*, somewhere in East Africa for guarding and exhibiting copies of the most representative intellectual products of the human experiment. Which may well lead to setting up the *Government of Earth* by the morally living intellectually able for the voluntarily joining decent and free.

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